

CHARACTERIZATION AND STRESS TOLERANCE OF YEASTS ISOLATED FROM PALM WINE

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ABSTRACT

Most traditional food fermentation processes are incomplete, resulting to products that are prone to rapid deterioration. This is due to the involvement of a mix of microbial strains that are spontaneously introduced from the environment. The selection and use of microbial strains that can tolerate the prevailing stressors during fermentation process will drive fermentation to completion and generate stable food products. Therefore, this study was carried out to characterize and determine the stress tolerance of yeast strains isolated from palm wine. Yeasts isolated from palm wine samples were characterized using phenotypic methods. Yeast isolates were assessed for tolerance to different concentrations of ethanol (4 - 16%) and NaCl (5 - 20%). Total yeast counts in the palm wine samples decreased from log 9 to 7 cfu/ml over 72 hours. Fifteen distinct yeast isolates were identified to belong to four different genera. They include: *Saccharomyces* (40%), *Candida* (13.33%), *Pichia* (26.67%) and *Kluyveromyces* (20%). *S. cerevisiae* PWB13 showed the greatest tolerance to ethanol (4 - 16%) while *P. ohmeri* PWB32 was the most sensitive strain. *S. cerevisiae* PWB13 had the highest percentage tolerance to NaCl (5 - 20%). *Candida* sp. PWA11 and *P. ohmeri* PWB32 were more sensitive to the different concentrations of NaCl. The yeast strains showed diversity in tolerance to stress conditions and some strains showed potentials to ensure complete fermentation of food substrates.

Keywords: Fermentation, Yeasts, Stress, Palm wine

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Palm wine is an alcoholic beverage, consumed throughout the tropics and produced by natural fermentation of highly sugary saps from oil palm (*Elaeis guineensis*) (Sanni *et al.*, 1999; Nwachukwu *et al.*, 2006). It is extremely popular in West and Central Africa, where it plays an important role in the culture of the people. Some of the local names for palm wine are *emu* in Nigeria and *nsafufuo* in Ghana. Although not scientifically or clinically proven, some health benefits that are associated with the consumption of palm wine based on indigenous knowledge include; improvement of sight, treatment of measles and rashes and relief from stomach disorder. Palm wine is predominantly fermented by yeasts (Amoa-Awua *et al.*, 2007). Yeasts have the potentials to improve the stability, nutritional value and organoleptic properties of foods. Also, they secrete bioactive metabolites into fermenting substrates (Jespersen, 2003; Abbas, 2006; Hellstrom *et al.*, 2010). However, these benefits are not optimally derived in palm wine because the production is by chance inoculation and uncontrolled fermentation process, generating products that vary in qualities, deteriorate rapidly and without proven health benefits (Sanni *et al.*, 1999; AmoA-Awua *et al.*, 2007).

There is a wide physiological diversity of yeasts in palm wine (Sanni and Lonner, 1993). Yeasts isolated from palm wine are used locally as traditional raising agents in bakery products and for the production of alcoholic beverages (Bechem *et al.*, 2007). The selection and use of technologically important yeast strains from palm wine microflora in a controlled fermentation process will generate products with desirable and predictable qualities. An

important requirement for the selection of microbial strains for starter culture development is the ability of the strain to tolerate the stressors that prevail during fermentation. The yeast will rapidly and efficiently complete the fermentation process (Holzapfel, 2002). The most important stressors during traditional fermentation of different food substrates include high concentration of salt, ethanol, sugar and organic acids (Belloch *et al.*, 2008). This study aims to characterize and determine the stress tolerance of yeasts isolated from palm wine.

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Collection of palm wine samples

Fresh palm wine samples were aseptically collected from retailers in sterile containers from Ebelle, Igueben Local Government Area, Edo State, Nigeria. The samples were transported to the laboratory for analysis within 2 hours.

2.2 Determination of pH and titratable acidity (TA) of palm wine

The pH of palm wine samples was determined at 24 hourly intervals over a period of 72 hours by using a pH meter (Jenway 3510, Staffordshire, UK). Titratable acidity (TA) was determined in triplicates at 24 hourly intervals over a period of 72 hours. It was determined by measuring 10ml of palm wine sample into a conical flask and titrated against 1.0 M NaOH with the use of phenolphthalein as indicator. The appearance of a pink colour indicated the end point. Readings were taken in triplicates. Titratable acidity was calculated according to AOAC (1990) using the formula below:

$$\text{Titratable acidity (g/100 ml)} = \frac{\text{Volume of NaOH}}{\text{Volume of sample}} \times 10$$

2.3 Enumeration and isolation of yeasts from palm wine

One (1) ml of palm wine sample was serially diluted into 9 ml of sterile distilled water. One ml of appropriate serial dilution was dispensed into petri-plate containing Yeast Peptone Dextrose Agar (YPDA) supplemented with 0.1 mg/ml of streptomycin sulphate to inhibit bacterial growth. The plates were incubated at 30 °C for 48 hours. The plates were examined and colonies formed were counted and recorded as colony forming unit per ml (cfu/ml) of the sample (Osho, 2005). Distinct yeast colonies from each plate were randomly selected and purified by repeated streaking on YPDA, without streptomycin. Pure culture of each yeast isolate was kept on YPDA agar slants, stored at 5 °C and renewed at 2 weekly intervals (Kurtzman *et al.*, 2011).

2.4 Characterization and identification of yeast isolates

Pure cultures of yeast strains were characterized morphologically and biochemically. Fifteen colonies of fresh cultures of yeast isolates were observed for texture, colour, surface, elevation and margin. Cellular morphology was determined by taking a portion of the yeast colony into drops of lactophenol cotton blue on a clean glass slide. The slides were examined under the microscope using the X40 objective lens (Kurtzman *et al.*, 2011). Biochemical properties determined include; acid production from glucose, hydrolysis of urea and sugar fermentation as described by Kurtzman *et al.* (2011). The sugars used include, glucose, sucrose, maltose, galactose and lactose. Yeast isolates were identified with reference to Sanni and Lonner (1993) and Boboye *et al.*, (2008).

2.5 Determination of stress tolerance by yeast

2.5.1 Ethanol tolerance

Ethanol tolerance by yeast strains was assessed by inoculating 5% fresh broth culture of each yeast strain into Erlenmeyer flasks with YEPD broth containing 4 to 16% ethanol (v/v) in triplicates. After inoculation, flasks were incubated at 30 °C for 24 hours. Samples were taken after 24 hours and optical density was recorded at 600 nm on UV-Visible Spectrophotometer (Jenway, 6305, Staffordshire, UK). A control flask contained the broth culture without ethanol. Ethanol tolerance was calculated using the formula below (Ali and Khan, 2014).

$$\text{Ethanol tolerance (\%)} = \frac{\text{Absorbance of test}}{\text{Absorbance of control}} \times 100$$

2.5.2 NaCl tolerance

The yeast strains were tested for NaCl tolerance by testing their growth in YEPD broth (in triplicates) containing: 0, 5, 10, 15 and 20 % of NaCl. Fresh culture of each yeast (5% v/v) was inoculated in triplicates into YPD broth and incubated for 24 hours at 30 °C. A control flask contained the same broth culture but without salt. Samples were taken after 24 hours and optical density was recorded at 600 nm using UV-visible spectrophotometer (Jenway, 6305, Staffordshire, UK) (Ali and Khan, 2014). Salt tolerance was calculated using the formula below:

$$\text{Salt tolerance (\%)} = \frac{\text{Absorbance of test}}{\text{Absorbance of control}} \times 100$$

2.6 Statistical analysis

Data were presented as mean \pm standard deviation of replicate readings.

3.0 RESULTS

Table 3.1 shows the pH and TA of the palm wine samples (PWA and PWB) over 72 hours. The pH and TA of both samples decreased and increased respectively with Sample PWB having greater increase in TA from 1.10 \pm 0.00 to 2.05 \pm 0.70 g/100 ml. Yeast counts decreased by at least a log order 1. Sample PWA had higher yeast counts of 8.81 log₁₀ cfu/ml after 72 hours (Table 3.2).

Table 3.1: pH and titratable acidity of the palm wine samples

Time (Hours)	pH		Titratable acidity (g/100 ml)	
	PWA	PWB	PWA	PWB
24	3.54	3.60	1.15 \pm 0.07	1.10 \pm 0.00
48	3.51	3.54	1.35 \pm 0.21	1.40 \pm 0.00
72	3.50	3.51	1.45 \pm 0.07	2.05 \pm 0.70

Values are mean \pm standard deviation of replicate readings

Key: Palm wine sample A: PWA; Palm wine sample B: PWB

Table 3.2: Yeast counts of palm wine samples

Time (Hours)	Log ₁₀ cfu/ml	
	PWA	PWB
24	9.41	9.37
48	9.26	9.23
72	8.81	7.00

Key: Palm wine sample A: PWA; Palm wine sample B: PWB

Based on distinct colonial morphology, fifteen isolates were randomly selected and purified. The isolates were identified to be species of the following genera after morphological and biochemical characterization; *Saccharomyces* (40%), *Candida* (13.33), *Pichia* (26.67%) and *Kluyveromyces* (20%). *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* had the highest percentage of occurrence (40%) while *Candida* spp. had the lowest (13.33%) (Figure 3.1). The results in Figure 3.2 show the ethanol tolerance of yeasts isolated from palm wine. The fifteen yeasts strains showed tolerance to 4% ethanol, *Candida* sp. PWA11 and *P. ohmeri* PWB 32 did not tolerate 8% ethanol. YPD broth with 16% ethanol was tolerated by three yeast strains; *S. cerevisiae* PWA14 and PWB13 and *P. membranefacien* PWA32. The highest tolerance to 16% ethanol was shown by strain PWB13. Thirteen of the fifteen yeast strains did not tolerate above 10% of NaCl. *S. cerevisiae* PWB13 is the only yeast strain that tolerated 20% NaCl (Figure 3.3).

Figure 3.1: Percentage occurrence of yeasts in palm wine

Figure 3.2: Ethanol tolerance of yeast isolates

Figure 3.3: Sodium chloride tolerance of yeast isolates

4.0 DISCUSSION

This study revealed the changes in the pH and titratable acidity of the palm wine samples (PWA and PWB) with respect to time. The pH of samples PWA and PWB decreased with the fermentation time while the titratable acidity increased. The decrease in pH and increase in titratable acidity are due to the accumulation of organic acids from the metabolic activities of microbes as reported by Ukpaka (2014) and Nwachukwu *et al.* (2006). In this study, yeast counts decreased with fermentation time. The increase in titratable acidity that was recorded in this study along with other stress factors that prevail during fermentation such as high concentration of ethanol and increase in temperature could be responsible for the reduction in yeast count (Abe *et al.*, 2009). Our observation is in agreement with the reports of Ukpaka (2014) and Obi *et al.* (2015). Ethanol is toxic to cells, reducing cell viability and leading to cell death (Abe *et al.*, 2009).

The yeast species identified in this study have been previously reported in palm wine (Sanni and Lonner, 1993; Ebabhi *et al.*, 2013; Ali and Khan 2014). They are also associated with other traditional fermented foods such as *burukutu*, *kunu zaki*, *nunu* and *ogi* (Sanni and Lonner, 1993; Aponte *et al.*, 2010; Akabanda *et al.*, 2012).

The stability and quality of fermented alcoholic beverages depends on the tolerance of the yeast starter culture to high concentration of ethanol, osmotic pressure and other stress conditions during fermentation (Belloch *et al.*, 2008). It is important to choose strains that will remain viable and metabolically active during fermentation to ensure efficient and complete fermentation (Lee *et al.*, 2011). Ethanol and sodium chloride are common stressors associated with the fermentation of several substrates. Alcohol content of some beverages such as beer and wine ranges from 2 to 7% and 12 to 20% respectively. Salt is a typical additive in bakery products. In the present study, we tested the tolerance of the yeast isolates to different concentrations of ethanol and salt. Most of the yeast strains showed tolerance to 4, 8 and 12% of ethanol, although at strain specific levels. In a related study, majority of *Saccharomyces* species were able to develop on plates containing 12% ethanol (Belloch *et al.*, 2008). Our report supports the observation that some indigenous yeast strains possess technological properties that are comparable to commercial starters (Martini, 1996). Only three strains; *S. cerevisiae* PWA14 and PWB13 and *P. membranefacien* PWA32 showed tolerance to 16% of ethanol. This potential is thought to be rare among indigenous yeast strains. Kumar *et al.* (2011) reported that *S. cerevisiae* isolated from *toddy* tolerated up to 15% of ethanol.

Selection and application of yeasts for traditional food bioprocessing such as dough making, meat and fish curing, cheese ripening and olive fermentation requires salt tolerant strains (Bechem *et al.*, 2007; Fakruddin *et al.*, 2013). Salt level can be up to 20% in cured meat. Our study revealed salt tolerance by yeast strains associated with palm wine. Twelve yeast strains tolerated up to 10% NaCl. However, only two; *K. africanus* PWA21 and *S. cerevisiae* PWB13 and a single strain; *S. cerevisiae* PWB13 tolerated 15 and 20 % NaCl respectively. Yeasts grow in substrates with high salt concentration (Lopandic *et al.*, 2006; Walker, 2009). Bonatsou *et al.* (2015) reported that the growth of *P. guilliermondii* Y16 was not inhibited by salt concentration of 109 g/L.

In conclusion, the study revealed the strain-specificity of the ethanol and sodium chloride tolerance by yeasts isolated from palm wine. We identified some yeast isolates that with potentials as starter culture for fermentation of foods with high concentrations of ethanol and sodium chloride.

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